

Intraoperative Incidence of Nausea & Vomiting in LSCS Under Spinal Anesthesia

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Abstract: Objective: To study the incidence of IONV (intraoperative nausea and vomiting) in LSCS (lower segment cesarean section) under spinal anesthesia. Methods: The data was analyzed by using SPSS version 20. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize patients' baseline socio-demographic data and the frequency of different variables (patient, anesthetic and surgical related variables). Continuous variables were presented as medians, i.e., mean ($\pm$ standard deviation (SD)) and categorical variables were presented as frequencies with corresponding proportions using tables. The chi-square test was used to compare frequencies of respondents with categorical variables. Independent variables were analyzed using binary and multivariate logistic regression with the dependent variable. Variables with a p-value of ≤ 0.2 from the bivariable analysis were fitted to a multivariable logistic regression to check their association with dependent outcome. Odds ratio with 95% confidence interval and the p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered to have a significant. Result: 316 Patients who underwent cesarean section with spinal anesthesia were participated in this study. The incidence of intraoperative nausea and vomiting was 42.4%. According to multivariable logistic regression, age greater than 30 years (OR, 6.26; 95%CI, 2.2–17.78; p-value 0.001), primiparous (OR, 3.72; 95%CI, 1.35–10.24; p-value, 0.011), having motion sickness (OR, 7.1; 95%CI, 2.75–18.33; p-value 0.001), emergency LSCS (OR, 9.85; 95%CI, 3.19–30.38; p-value 0.001), oxygen supplementation (OR, 0.021; 95%CI, 0.005–0.08; p-value 0.0001) and uterotonic agent (OR, 2.99; 95%CI 1.24–7.22; p-value 0.015) had statistically significant association with intraoperative nausea and vomiting. Conclusion: In this study, the overall incidence of intraoperative nausea and vomiting after spinal anesthesia was 42.4%. Parturients with age greater than 30 years, having motion sickness, didn't get intraoperative supplemental oxygen, oxytocin used for the uterotonic purpose, emergency surgery, and primiparous were at increased risk of intraoperative nausea and vomiting.

Keywords: Spinal anesthesia, intraoperative nausea and vomiting (IONV), lower segment cesarean section.

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Introduction

Nausea and vomiting (N&V) are common complications encountered during a lower segment cesarean section (LSCS) performed under spinal anesthesia. These symptoms, while often perceived as minor, can significantly impact the patient's experience and the surgical process. Understanding the etiology, preventative measures, and management

strategies for N&V in this context is crucial for enhancing maternal comfort and ensuring procedural efficiency. LSCS, commonly referred to as a cesarean delivery, is a frequently performed surgical procedure worldwide. Spinal anesthesia is preferred for cesarean sections due to its rapid onset, reliable sensory and motor block, and minimal fetal exposure to anesthetic drugs. However, spinal anesthesia is associated with a notable incidence of intraoperative nausea and vomiting, reported in 50-80% of cases without prophylactic intervention. Several mechanisms contribute to N&V during LSCS under spinal anesthesia. One primary factor is hypotension, a common side effect of spinal anesthesia, which results from sympathetic blockade and subsequent vasodilation [1]. The decreased blood pressure reduces perfusion to vital organs, including the brain, triggering nausea and vomiting through central mechanisms.

Another significant contributor is visceral stimulation. During cesarean delivery, manipulation of the uterus and other intra-abdominal organs can activate vagal afferent fibers, leading to the emetic response. This is exacerbated by the physiological and anatomical changes of pregnancy, such as the elevated diaphragm and increased intra-abdominal pressure. Moreover, the use of intrathecal opioids, although beneficial for analgesia, can potentiate N&V by stimulating the chemoreceptor trigger zone (CTZ) in the medulla. Additionally, psychological factors, such as anxiety and fear associated with surgery and childbirth, can further heighten susceptibility to nausea and vomiting [2].

During the intraoperative period, maintaining stable hemodynamics is critical. The use of vasopressors like phenylephrine or ephedrine to counteract hypotension is a common practice. These medications help maintain blood pressure and reduce the risk of N&V. Additionally, positioning the patient with a left lateral tilt can prevent aortocaval compression by the gravid uterus, further stabilizing blood pressure. Adequate analgesia without excessive opioid use is also important. While intrathecal opioids provide effective pain relief, their emetogenic potential necessitates careful dosing and possibly adjunctive use of non-opioid analgesics [3-5].

Postoperative management includes continued antiemetic therapy as needed and effective pain control strategies to minimize the use of opioids. Non-pharmacological interventions, such as reassurance and a calm environment, can also alleviate anxiety and reduce the incidence of postoperative nausea and vomiting. To prevent IONV during cesarean section (LSCS), blood pressure must be closely monitored, use of opioids must be kept to a minimum, the operative technique must be gentle with minimum displacement of the uterus (not exteriorizing through an incision), and uterotonics and antibiotics must be administered in dilute and slow infusions [6,7]. Knowing the magnitude and factors causing IONV helps urgent need for safety and treatment in the service of anesthesia to prevent its impact on surgery and patient satisfaction. Therefore, this study aimed to determine the magnitude and associated factors of IONV during cesarean section under SA.

Research Methodology

A total of 316 patients who gave birth by cesarean section under spinal anesthesia from October 2023 to March 2024 at Madhesh Institute of Health Sciences, Janakpur, Nepal were included in the study. Data were collected and entered into SPSS version 20 for statistical analysis. Categorical sociodemographic data were summarized by frequencies and percentages. The chi-square test was used to compare frequencies of respondents with categorical variables. Independent variables were analyzed using binary and multivariate logistic regression with the dependent variable. Variables with a p-value of ≤ 0.2 from the bivariable analysis were included in a multivariable logistic regression to assess their association with the dependent outcome. An odds ratio with a 95% confidence interval and a p-value of ≤ 0.05 were considered significant. The data collection tool was prepared based on relevant literature from around the world. Perioperative anesthetic and surgical management were observed by data collectors who were not involved in the anesthetic management of the patients. Vital signs of each participant were recorded during the surgery. The fluid used for preloading or co-loading and the anesthetic and surgical interventions during spinal anesthesia in the operating theater were documented.

Results

A total of 316 patients were selected for the study. The majority (60.4%) of the patients were aged ≤ 30 years and 56.96% of them had a BMI of between 18.5 and 24.9 kg/m². The mean age and BMI of the patients were 29.57 ± 5.5 and 24.7 ± 3.6 respectively. Most of them are unemployed (72.8%) in workplaces.

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age	>30	125
	<30	191
BMI	18.5-24.9	180
	>25	136
Employment	Employed	86
	Unemployed	230
Motion sickness	Yes	122
	No	194

All patients were given 0.5% bupivacaine for spinal anesthesia purposes, with or without opioid adjuvants. The majority (60.4%) of spinal anesthesia was done with greater than or equal to 2.2 ml bupivacaine. Of all the participants, around 134 (42.4%) of patients complained of intraoperative nausea and vomiting after spinal anesthesia. From the participants, around 54 (17.08%), 17 (5.4%), and 63 (19.9%) of patients developed nausea only, vomiting only, and both nausea and vomiting, respectively. Around 126 (39.87%) of participants were hypotensive at the 10th minute after spinal anesthesia was administered, with a ≥20mmhg decrement from the baseline MAP (Mean Arterial Pressure). According to multivariable analysis, age greater than 30 years (OR, 6.26; 95%CI, 2.2–17.78; p-value 0.001), primiparous (OR, 3.72; 95% CI, 1.35–10.24; p-value, 0.011), having motion sickness (OR, 7.1; 95% CI, 2.75–18.33; p-value 0.001), emergency LSCS (OR, 9.85; 95%CI, 3.19–30.38; p-value 0.001), Oxygen supplementation (OR, 0.021; 95%CI, 0.005–0.08; p-value 0.0001), and uterotonic agent (OR, 2.99; 95%CI 1.24–7.22; p-value 0.015) are significant factors for the development of IONV.

Table 2: Incidence of IONV in related with different factors of patients who gave birth with cesarean section under spinal anesthesia (n = 316; with chi-square test)

Variable	IONV=134(42.4%)	NO IONV=182(57.6%)	P value
Age	>30	30	0.11
	< 30	104	
BMI	18.5-24.9	97	0.35
	>25	37	
Parity	Primipara	59	0.009
	Multipara	75	
Previous anesthesia	Yes	56	0.6
	No	78	
Motion sickness	Yes	83	0.001
	No	51	
Intraoperative pain	Yes	41	1
	No	93	
Type of surgery	Emergency	116	0.001
	Elective	18	
Dexamethasone	Yes	104	0.06
	No	30	
NPO hrs	<6hrs	89	0.002
	>6hrs	45	
Opioid	Yes	71	0.002

	No	63	155	
Supplemental O2	Yes	122	63	0.0001
	No	12	119	
≥ 20 mmhg of baseline MAP	Yes	81	45	0.02
	No	53	137	

Table 3: Factors associated with the incidence of IONV for patients who underwent cesarean section with spinal anesthesia (Bivariable and Multivariable logistic regression).

Variable	OR, 95% CI & P- value
Age	>30 < 30
Parity	Primipara Multipara
Motion sickness	Yes No
Type of surgery	Emergency Elective
Supplemental O2	Yes No
Uterotonic agent	Oxytocin others

Discussion

Nausea and vomiting are common in a wide variety of surgical operations. However, this problem arises even more often in cesarean operations under spinal anesthesia. The incidence of IONV is as high as 80% in "high-risk" inpatients during the 24 hours after the operation and is dependent on the anesthesia technique used, together with preventative and therapeutic measures employed by the anesthetist [8]. Intraoperative nausea and vomiting after spinal anesthesia in cesarean delivery are a common occurrence with high incidences. The well-being of patients may be severely compromised as 72% of patients are afraid of NV and 71% feel significant discomfort [9,10]. This study was performed to assess the magnitude and possible risk factors associated with intraoperative nausea and vomiting during a cesarean section under spinal anesthesia. This can help the clinical environment if we know the possible factors, especially preventable factors, and contribute to improving patients' satisfaction in the perioperative period. Knowledge of independent IONV risk factors is crucial for the optimal use of antiemetic prophylaxis and multimodal management strategies [11]. The overall magnitude of IONV in this current study was 42.4%, which is almost similar to the study done at the University of Gondar on 373 parturients with an overall incidence of IONV of 40.8%. This similarity might be due to similar characteristics in sociodemographic and clinical setups of the study areas [12,13]. But the result of the present study is quite higher than the study done in Cape Town on 258 parturients, with an overall incidence of IONV of around 33%. This small variation might be due to differences in sociodemographic characteristics of the participants and the clinical setup difference. Also, the study was done only on elective type of surgery but the present study was done both on elective and emergency surgeries. The type of study can be another possible justification for this variation, as the previous study was done under a controlled approach with different protocols that limit the dose of medications and preload [14]. Another study showed that the incidence of IONV was 9.1%, which is lower compared to our study. Because the previous study was done by giving special concern and strict application for the prophylactic medications of nausea and vomiting and prevention of the possible risk factors of the complications. But in our study, 71% of parturients got antiemetic premedication [15]. Also, a study done on 209 patients to predict the possible factors of IONV

revealed that the overall incidence of IONV was 77 (36.8%) patients experienced nausea during the cesarean operation and 19 (9.1%) suffered from vomiting [10]. In our study, IONV was significantly associated with a maternal history of motion sickness (AOR = 7.1; 95% CI = 2.75–18.33 and p-value 0.001). Parturients having motion sickness are around seven times riskier to develop IONV. The possible mechanisms can best be justified by a spectrum of susceptibility to vestibular-mediated stimulus, which lowers the threshold for nausea and vomiting with motion. Changes in position and transfer on a stretcher at the end of surgery can stimulate afferent neural pathways that project to the vestibular nuclei, leading to activation of the brainstem nuclei, triggering the somatic and gastrointestinal components of emesis [10,15]. In this study, mothers who underwent emergency cesarean section had a significantly associated risk of IONV compared with their elective counterparts (OR = 9.85; 95% CI = 3.19–30.38; p-value = 0.001). Emergency-based C/S were approximately 10 times riskier for IONV, and this finding is in line with a study done by Aberie et al. at Addis Ababa Ethiopia in determining the Magnitude and associated factors of nausea and vomiting during cesarean section under spinal anesthesia [16]. Most of the factors predisposing to IONV during a cesarean section under spinal anesthesia are mostly specific to CS. In our study, parturients who took oxytocin for uterotonic purposes were significantly associated with IONV (OR = 9.85; 95% CI = 3.19–30.38; p-value = 0.001). In agreement with this, the overall incidence of Nausea and vomiting was 29% and 9% respectively after the mothers had been given oxytocin infusion. IONV mainly occurs as a result of hypotension produced by oxytocin administration [15]. In our study, a younger age of the parturient was associated with nausea and vomiting in the intraoperative period (OR = 6.26; 95% CI = 2.2–17.78; p = 0.001). Parturients being greater than 30 years of age were six times riskier for the development of IONV. This finding is supported by many literatures, even though nausea and vomiting they encountered were not merely in the intraoperative period and a group of patients were different [17–19]. Our study also revealed that the administration of supplemental oxygen during cesarean section was significantly associated with a decreased outcome of IONV. Most of the parturients who had intraoperative 100% supplemental oxygen with a facemask did not develop nausea and vomiting. Other studies also reported that supplemental oxygen is effective in preventing nausea and vomiting (OR = 0.021; 95% CI = 0.005–0.08; p-value = 0.0001). Oxygen concentration greater than or equal to 80% can decrease nausea and vomiting; it is found to be as effective or better than ondansetron [20,21]. But a systematic review and meta-analysis of controlled trials revealed that the administration of a higher concentration of oxygen had a weak beneficial effect in preventing nausea and vomiting, but their study was among patients who underwent general anesthesia [22,23]. According to our study primiparous parturients were at high risk of developing IONV with an OR of 3.72; 95%CI of 1.35–10.24 and p-value-0.01. This may be due to psychological factors.

Conclusion

In this study, the overall incidence of intraoperative nausea and vomiting after spinal anesthesia was 42.4%. Parturients with age greater than 30 years, having motion sickness, didn't get intraoperative supplemental oxygen, oxytocin used for the uterotonic purpose, emergency surgery, and primiparous were at an increased risk of intraoperative nausea and vomiting. This study was conducted within a short period with a small size of participants without sample size calculation analysis which leads to a wider confidence interval of the results. Additionally, this study failed to assess the long-rank effects of IONV on the quality of care and maternal satisfaction.

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